

Improvement of the purification performance of the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) of stabilization ponds type: Removal of sulfate and nitrate ions by adsorption onto micro-particles of shrimp-shells

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Abstract : The purpose of this study carried out at the Tiznit wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) is to evaluate the purification performance of the conventional stabilization ponds type process and, on the other hand, to improve the purification performance by using adsorption process based on novel inert natural materials of animal origin. This project is part of a sustainable development approach, aimed to improve the purification performance of WWTP by introducing low-cost, abundant and inexpensive solid inert biomaterials (SIBM). This adsorption process is recognized as one of the best water treatment techniques, more and more works are oriented towards the search for new materials, cheaper and having a good adsorbent potential. The results obtained with decanted raw wastewater (RWWD) and purified wastewater (PWW) are encouraging and show significant purification yields: 52 % and 48 % for sulfate ions and 43 % and 47 % for nitrate ions, respectively, for RWWD and PWW.

Keywords: Wastewater; Adsorption; Shrimp-shells; Nitrates; Sulfates.

1. Introduction

In recent years, considerable attention has been devoted to the study of different types of low-cost materials as adsorbents such as bark tree, charcoal, alum sludge, red mud, peanut, peat, corn cobs, cocoa shells and other waste for the adsorption of certain toxic substances to the environment [1]. The study of the chemical composition of shrimp shell particles in previous work has shown that this biomaterial is rich in proteins, polypeptides and other biomolecules such as chitin and its derivatives which are wholly or partially involved in ion retention [2-5]. Because of their high adsorption capacity, chitin and its derivatives are used as chelating agents for cations and metal ions such as, Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} [6]. The chelating power of these substances is explained by the presence of the acetylamine group ($-\text{NHCOCH}_3$) and the amine group ($-\text{NH}_2$) on the chitin and chitosan polymers [7].

The environment in Morocco, like all developing countries, is under tremendous pressure, particularly for population growth, urbanization and the needs generated by economic development. The volume of wastewater generated in Morocco was estimated at 500 Mm^3 in 2000 and is expected to reach 900 Mm^3 by the year 2020 [8]. The cost of environmental degradation accounts is nearly 20 billion dirhams annually, ie about 8.2 % of the national GDP [9]. In conjunction to this, the episodic droughts has to be considered; it is such a problematic that is not only limited to the quantity of water resources, but also to the quality which must be well managed. In this regard of water scarcity, the major

concern is to protect and rationalize water consumption. The advanced treatment and reuse of purified wastewater in the field of agriculture is therefore an indispensable solution in order to comply with the regulations implemented in this field. The shortage of water resources and the difficulties of its mobilization pushed the local authorities of Tiznit city to take into consideration the wastewater treatment. Treating wastewater will guarantee the protection of the underground water resources and the production of a new water source which can be used in agriculture. The adopted method for wastewater treatment in Tiznit is the natural lagooning [10].

The aim of this work is to improve the station's purification performance by using shrimp-shells inert biomaterials in adsorption separation technology, which is today one of the most important separation technologies [11-13], in order to attenuate the nitrate ion contents which are responsible for the phenomenon of eutrophication [14] and the excessive development of algae in the facultative and maturation ponds [15] and also the foul odors caused by transformation of sulfate ions into hydrogen sulfide in addition to the negative impact of effluent releases on the environment is indisputable [16].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Description of the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) of Tiznit

The city of Tiznit is the capital of the province of the same name and is part of the region of Souss Massa. It

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is about 90 km from Agadir and 14 km from the Atlantic coast. Its Lambert coordinates are: X = 81.5, Y = 308 and Z = 240 m general leveling of Morocco (NGM). The system adopted at the Tiznit wastewater treatment plant is the stabilization ponds system, which is a simple process in its design but complex in the biological processes involved in the treatment of wastewater. The treatment is carried out in large ponds. These ponds use the photosynthesis of algae to provide oxygen to pollution-degrading bacteria [17]. Fig.2 shows the different stages of wastewater treatment from upstream to downstream of WWTP.

Each basin contributes to the overall purification of wastewater as follows:

- Pretreatment (screening, sandblasting) at the entrance of the WWTP;
- Primary treatment by four anaerobic ponds (capacity 4900 m³/day), for a retention time of 3 days, which have the role of decanting the suspended matter and the degradation of the carbonaceous organic matter;
- Secondary treatment by four facultative ponds, which have large dimensions and are designed for BOD₅ removal
- Tertiary treatment by three series maturation ponds, which have medium to large sizes, receive the effluent from the facultative ponds and their size and number depends on the required bacteriological quality of the final effluent.

For sludge treatment, there are 4 drying beds, in order to dewater the sludge from the anaerobic ponds.

2.2. Sampling

The sampling method adopted is composite type in 24 hours in order to obtain a representative sample. Sampling points were taken at the inlet and outlet of the treatment plant. The samples were taken in polyethylene bottles. Transport to laboratory of the sample bottles was carried out in a cooler at a low temperature (+4°C) [18]. The characterization was

focused on the determination of in situ physicochemical parameters (water temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, electrical conductivity) which were measured on site, while the mineral parameters and the major parameters of pollution (Five-day biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅), chemical oxygen demand (COD) and total suspended solids (TSS)) were analyzed in the laboratory using accredited techniques and methods.

In order to determine the concentration of fecal coliforms in raw and purified wastewater, grab samples were taken in the morning at 1 pm. The choice of this sampling time corresponds to the maximum bacterial load of the raw sewage on the one hand and on the other hand to the intensity of the solar radiation which has a bactericidal effect on the elimination of fecal coliforms at outlet from the maturation ponds [18]. Wastewater samples for microbiological analyzes were collected in sterile glass containers [18]. During this period, we collected the wastewater at the inlet and outlet of the WWTP in order to get an idea of the purification efficiency of the plants.

2.3. Physico-chemical parameters

The parameters that were evaluated in this study are the parameters on site namely: air temperature (Alla France-type thermometer); water temperature and pH (portable pH-meter type WTW pH 3310 SET) [18]; electrical conductivity (conductivity meter type WTW Cond 3310 SET) [18]; dissolved oxygen (portable oximeter type WTW Oxi 3310 SET) [18]; In addition to the major pollution parameters, namely: chemical oxygen demand COD (colorimetric method) [19]; biochemical oxygen demand measured after five days BOD₅ (electrometric method) [20]; total suspended solids TSS and total volatile solids TVS (gravimetric method) [21]; nitrate NO₃⁻-N (Cadmium Reduction Method) [18]; ammoniacal nitrogen NH₄⁺-N (colorimetric method) [22]; total Kjeldahl Nitrogen TKN (Acid digestion-colorimetric method) [23] and sulfate ions SO₄²⁻ (Nephelometric method) [18].

Fig.1. Schema of the wastewater treatment plants of the Tiznit.

2.4. Bacteriological parameters

The study of the bacteriological parameters concerned the quantification of the parameters of fecal origin: fecal coliforms (FC). The FC count was conducted using the indirect method of multiple tube fermentation in a lactose broth, and the number was then statistically deduced using the most probable number (MPN) method by inoculation of tubes in liquid media [18].

2.5. Preparation of the adsorbent based on shrimp-shells

Shrimp-shells wastes were recovered at the port of Agadir (south-west Morocco). Prior to use, they were rinsed several times with tap water, and they were air-dried for 2-3 days and then ground and sieved with a grain size of less than or equal to 500 μm . The study of the adsorption of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions on shrimp-shells wastes was carried out under static conditions (Fig.3). This system makes it possible to have a better contact between the adsorbent and the adsorbate and avoid any decantation of the adsorbent.

In this batch adsorption experiments, 40 ml of wastewater solution with a given ions concentration, C_{i0} , was mixed with 1 g of micro-particles of shrimp-shells without any pre-treatment, the mixture being vigorously stirred with the use of a magnetic stirrer and was maintained in water bath thermostat, at a constant temperature of 25 $^\circ\text{C}$ in a water bath thermostat. The time required to reach the adsorption equilibrium for a given initial ion concentration was determined by sampling aliquots of analyzed solution for different times.

Before analyzing the requested parameters, the sampled solutions were filtered on Whatman paper of 0.45 μm porosity. The quantity of a pollutant adsorbed and retained by an adsorbent can be expressed as the retained concentration C_{ir} , the quantity retained per gram of the material Q_{ir} or the retention rate P_i .

$$C_{ir} = C_{i0} - C_{ie} \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{ir} = (C_{i0} - C_{ie})V/m \quad (2)$$

$$P_i (\%) = (1 - C_{ie} / C_{i0}) \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

C_{ir} : Removed Concentration of pollutant i (g/L)

C_{i0} : Initial concentration of the pollutant i (g/L)

C_{ie} : Residual concentrations of pollutant i at equilibrium (g/L)

Q_{ir} : Equilibrium adsorption capacity of adsorbed pollutant i (mg/g)

m : Mass ratio of the adsorbent (g)

V : Volume of the adsorbate (L)

P_i : Removal percentage of the pollutant i (%)

Fig.2. Experimental device used for the study of adsorption under static conditions

2.6. Physico-chemical characterization of shrimp-shells wastes

The protein content was found to vary between 30% and 40% of the dry weight, the chitin content varied between 20% and 30% and 30-50% of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) [2-5]. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), also known as SEM analysis or SEM microscopy, is used very effectively in microanalysis and failure analysis of solid inorganic materials. Electron microscopy is performed at high magnifications, generates high-resolution images and precisely measures very small features and objects. The biomaterial used is characterized, in the course of our previous work, by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Model: Hitachi S-4500 SEM (Particle size <500 microns).

The adsorbent powder is not homogeneous; it is made up of large grains of different size and morphologies (Fig.3), which confirms the heterogeneity of the surface of this raw biomaterial. The images also show the pore nature of the crude ground with diversity in the size and texture of the pores, which proves the existence of very large internal specific surfaces.

EDX is usually used to analyze the elemental constitution of solid samples. Fig.4 illustrates the energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) of shrimp shell in the raw state, which has also been analyzed by our team at the European Institute of Membranes in Montpellier (France). This spectrum presents the chemical elements that make up the structure of this substance as well as their mass and atomic percentages. It shows that the shrimp shell particles, in addition to carbon, oxygen, the major constituents of proteins, chitin, and bicarbonates, the main components of the shrimp shell, is also composed largely of calcium. This confirms that the majority of bicarbonates are composed of calcium bicarbonates.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of raw and purified wastewater of Tiznit

In order to compare the purification performance amelioration of the solid inert biomaterial with stabilization ponds adopted for WWTP of the Tiznit. A study of the polluting load of wastewater used was carried out. Table 1 presents the physico-chemical and microbiological parameters of the raw wastewater decanted (RWW) and purified wastewater (PWW) of the WWTP Tiznit.

The qualitative analysis of the raw wastewater entering the WWTP shows that they present a concentration almost similar to the typology of the urban waste waters of Morocco [10]. The qualitative analysis of purified wastewater at the outlet of maturation ponds shows that the carbon loading in terms of COD, BOD5 and TSS complies with the specific limit values for domestic discharges [24], with purification efficiencies of the order of 87 % for TSS, 90 % for COD and 87 % for BOD5. Concerning fecal coliforms, the abatement exceeds 97 %. The results obtained at the outlet of maturation ponds conform to the Moroccan standard of water intended for irrigation (FC 1000/100mL) [25]. The reuse of purified wastewater from the WWTP of Tiznit is an achievement for the national office of electricity and drinking water and also a necessity to reduce the water deficit in order to meet the growing demands arriving at the office from riparian farmers who used previously untreated sewage, to which is added an important economic value thanks to fertilizing nutrients.

Table 1

Pollution load of wastewater used from WWTP Tiznit

Parameter	RWWD	PWW
T (°C)	27.6	27.9
pH	7.84	8.55
Electrical conductivity (µs/cm)	1380	1490
Dissolved oxygen (mg O ₂ /L)	0	6.2
TSS (mg/L)	540	67
BOD5 (mg O ₂ /L)	460	60
COD (mg O ₂ /L)	1147	117
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg P/L)	25	12
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg N/L)	8,8	41
NH ₄ ⁺ (mg N/L)	58	31
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	309	264
Fecal coliforms (UFC/100 mL)	3.2 10 ⁶	200

Fig.3. SEM images of shrimp shell particle

Fig.4. EDX spectrum of shrimp shell particles

The purified wastewater (PWW) at the outlet of the WWTP is in compliance with the Moroccan domestic waste standard [24]. Nevertheless, NO_3^- ions contribute to the excessive development of algae in the facultative and maturation ponds and have a detrimental effect on compliance with the thresholds set by the Moroccan standard for domestic discharges [24] for normative pollution parameters and also the Moroccan standard for the reuse of purified wastewater [25], because the proliferation of algae is a phenomenon which often hinders the reduction of the major parameters of pollution in the paths of stabilization ponds by the increase of the contents of TSS and consequently the elevation of the contents in term of BOD5 and COD [26]. The evolution of nitrogenous forms in maturation ponds depends particularly on the presence of dissolved oxygen [1]. The absorption by algae and the recycling by the zooplankton can reduce considerably the concentrations to NH_4^+ in the environment. This nitrification appears to be more active during periods of low organic loads [1], for this purpose, the removal of nitrate ions is very low. The residual concentration remains high in the treated effluent and could constitute a great risk of eutrophication for these discharges which are intended for irrigation.

Concerning sulfate ions, the main origin of odors arises from the production and emission of hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), which is considered to be the major component of sulfide. It is produced by sulfato-reducing bacteria mainly desulfovibrios which reduce sulfates to sulfides [27]. For this purpose, our research team has considered solutions to improve the purifying performance and to produce clean water of good quality for irrigation, and to remedy, on the one hand, the problem of excessive algal growth occurring in most wastewater treatment plants with stabilization ponds process and, on the other hand, the foul odors caused by the presence of sulphate ions at the water level wastewater treatment plant. Our study is part of a sustainable development approach, aiming at improving the purification performance of WWTP by introducing adsorbent biomaterials, abundant and inexpensive, hence the valorization of the biomaterials of the region.

3.2. Study of adsorption of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions by SIBM

3.2.1. Adsorption of Nitrate ions

Fig.5 shows the evolution of the concentration of the nitrate ions contained in the RWWD and PWW of the WWTP of Tiznit as function of contact time for shrimp shell particles ($R = 25 \text{ g/L}$, $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$). It is noted that the equilibrium time is independent of the concentration and that the amount adsorbed at equilibrium increases with the concentration. Moreover, it is observed that the initial rate of adsorption increases with the concentration, this being due to the fact that the diffusion of nitrate ions from the solution to the surface of the adsorbent is

accelerated by increasing the concentration [28]. The appearance of these curves does not make it possible to distinguish two different stages of adsorption, everything happens as if the adsorption is done in a single step. The retained concentration of nitrate ions by shrimp shell particles reaches a maximum of 3.77 mg/L and 19.40 mg/L respectively for RWWD and PWW. The equilibrium is reached after a contact time of approximately 30 min.

The difference in the retained quantity of nitrate ions for the wastewater studied could be explained by the initial concentration of each polluting charge.

3.2.2. Adsorption of Sulfate ions

Fig.6 shows the variation in the retained concentration of sulfate ions by shrimp shell particles as a function of contact time ($R = 25\text{g/L}$, $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$), contained in the RWWD and PWW of the WWTP of Tiznit. The analysis of this curve reveals that the concentration retained by shrimp shell particles increases rapidly with the contact time, the plateau representing the adsorption equilibrium is practically achieved after about 1 hour for the two types of wastewater studied. This binding to shrimp shell particles could be explained by positive charges of the acetyl groups, amines and proteins.

Fig.5. Effect of contact time on the removal of nitrate ions by shrimp shell particles for RWWD and PWW.

Fig.6. Effect of contact time on the removal of sulfate ions by shrimp shell particles for RWWD and PWW.

3.2.2. Purification performance of SIBM

In order to evaluate the purification performance of SIBM used on the studied ions, the concentrations of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions in the wastewater before and after the adsorption are presented below (Table 2). From these results, it can be seen that the NO_3^- ions have high

purification yields of the order of 42.84% and 47.31%, respectively, for RWWD and PWW. In the case of SO_4^{2-} ions, it is noted that shrimp shell particles present high purification yields of the order of 51.91% and 48.43%, respectively, for the RWWD and PWW.

Table 2

Concentration of NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions in wastewater before and after adsorption equilibrium

		NO_3^- (mg/L)	SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)
RWWD	Before adsorption	8.8	309
	After adsorption	5.03	148.6
	Removal percentage (%)	42.84	51.91
PWW	Before adsorption	41	264
	After adsorption	21.6	136.15
	Removal percentage (%)	47.31	48.43

4. Conclusion

The pollutant load of raw sewage from the WWTP of Tiznit has concentrations almost similar to the typology of Moroccan urban wastewater for the major parameters of carbon and nitrogen pollution because the WWTP receives only domestic wastewater.

Concerning the purified wastewater of WWTP of Tiznit, the purification yields recorded by stabilization ponds system for the parameters of BOD_5 , COD and TSS are satisfactory, and for the parameters studied, namely NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions, the results obtained show that the system of stabilization ponds is not sufficient alone to have purified waters adequate for agricultural reuse and even for preservation of the natural environment. The residual concentrations remain very high in the treated effluent and could constitute a great risk of eutrophication for releases in sensitive medium and for the SO_4^{2-} ions, It is also observed that the removal of these ions by stabilization ponds system is weak. Therefore, the search for new unconventional cleaning processes based on SIBM which would be inexpensive and easy to implement is strongly recommended in order to improve the quality of purified water according to the required standards. Moreover, the purification yields of the NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions by shrimp shell particles are important. Then shrimp shell particles could constitute a potential adsorbent of the pollutants NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} , considering its low cost and the retention rate which is important. Such a process can be used in the purification of wastewater and could integrate in the purification system of the WWTP of Tiznit in order to

improve the purification yield and to comply with the Moroccan regulations in force.

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